

A Community Group's Introduction to Business Archives: The Value of Corporate Heritage

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In this blog, [Nella McNicol](#) from the [OHOS Archives Lab](#) at the [University of Glasgow](#) discusses the experience of staff and volunteers from [the Pipe Factory](#) during the introductory session to Business Archives hosted at [University of Glasgow Archives and Special Collections](#) by archivist [Kiara King](#) from [The Ballast Trust](#).

In the heart of the East End of Glasgow lies an important historical landmark in the city's industrial heritage. Situated in the 100-year-old [Barras market](#), a once-thriving Pipe Factory operated by William White and Sons between 1877 and 1955 employed over 500 people, significantly impacting the Calton community. Fast forward nearly 70 years later, a dedicated community group has taken on the crucial task of [refiring the pipe factory](#) and have become the custodians of this historic site. They seek to offer heritage-themed learning opportunities to preserve its stories and artefacts for future generations.

In August 2024, volunteers and staff embarked on a day trip to the University of Glasgow Archives and Special Collections. They were provided with an introductory session to business archives from archivist Kiara King of The Ballast Trust, a charitable foundation that provides a rescue, sorting and cataloguing service for business archives. This experience not only broadened their understanding but also ignited a deeper passion for the vital work needed to safeguard the historical narratives they hold dear.

The session began with Kiara's tour of the repository, highlighting its search rooms and some of the most well-known and visited collections. Kiara noted some challenges when attempting to engage users with business archives, with many assuming that the materials they hold are only for academic purposes. The value of business archives becomes much more apparent when considered as corporate heritage. Often, with business archives, you don't know what you're expecting. This was certainly true for the Pipe Factory, where discarded clay pipe fragments were discovered hidden in various corners of the building earlier this year.

One of the key benefits of this visit was the ability to forge connections between the community heritage groups, an academic archive and the broader history of industry in the area. The repository was home to a wealth of knowledge about other East End businesses that contributed to Glasgow's economic development. The volunteers had the rare opportunity to explore materials related to [Templeton's Carpet Factory](#), another former industrial powerhouse of the city and neighbour to the Pipe Factory. They were able to handle old sales records, photographs of staff portraits and the factory at the height of its success, and documentation about the carpet-making process.

Moreover, the experience reinforced the value of collaboration and community involvement. By connecting with archivists like Kiara, the group had the opportunity to learn the basic knowledge required to set up a business archive, exploring issues such as copyright and patents, data protection, environmental controls, and the value of corporate heritage from a seasoned expert. This offered the volunteers a better understanding of the materials they are likely to work with and an appreciation for how these might benefit their local community.

Perhaps the most heartening benefit of their experience was the group's renewed sense of purpose. Engaging with the collections in the repository sparked discussions about future projects and the possibilities that arise from utilising their own archival materials. The visit to the business archive proved to be an invaluable experience for the group dedicated to preserving the legacy of the Pipe Factory. They gained new insights and connections that reignited their commitment to valuing their corporate and industrial heritage. Their experiences remind us of the importance of preserving local history and the stories that shape our identities as a community. Through collaboration, education, and shared passion, this session provided the building blocks to ensure that The Pipe Factory continues to live on.

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